

TWO GRAPH FUNCTIONS OF MBK-OPEN SETS

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ABSTRACT

We introduce the concepts contra δ -b-closed graphs and strongly contra mbk-closed graphs for mbk-open sets and obtain some properties of them.

Keywords: mbk-open sets, mbk-closed graphs, contra mbk-closed graphs, contra mbk-continuous functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, spaces (X, τ) and (Y, φ) (briefly, X and Y) always state topological spaces without any separation axiom. If $A \subseteq X$, closure and interior of A in X are indicated by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. The notion of regular open sets is important several in branches of mathematics. A subset A is called regular open[11] (resp. regular closed[11] if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). Of course, regular closedness is complement of regular openness. The δ -interior of a subset A of X is the union of all regular open sets of X contained A and it is denoted by $\delta\text{-int}(A)$. A is called δ -open[12] iff $A = \delta\text{-int}(A)$. δ -open sets in X forms a topology τ_δ so that $\tau_\delta \subseteq \tau$ and the regular open sets of X form a base for τ_δ . The δ -closure of a subset A of X is the intersection of all regular closed sets of X containing A and it is denoted by $\delta\text{-cl}(A)$. A is called δ -closed[12] iff $A = \delta\text{-cl}(A)$.

We recall some definitions.

Definition 1.1. A space (X, τ) is called

(1) Urysohn[4] if for each $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$, there exist open sets U and V so that $x_1 \in U$, $x_2 \in V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(2) T_1 [5] if for each $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$, there exist mbk-open sets U and V so that $x_1 \in U$, $x_2 \in V$, $x_1 \notin V$, $x_2 \notin U$.

(3) T_2 [3] if for each $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$, there exist mbk-open sets U and V so that $x_1 \in U$, $x_2 \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

(4) mbk- T_2 [2] if for each $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$, there exist mbk-open sets U and V so that $x_1 \in U$, $x_2 \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

Definition 1.2. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is called mbk-continuous[3] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is mbk-open in X for every open sets V of Y .

2. CHARACTERIZATIONS MBK-CLOSED AND CONTRA MBK-CLOSED GRAPHS

In this part, firstly we obtain some properties of mbk-closed graph functions. Then, we introduce two classes of graphs, namely, contra mbk-closed graphs and strongly contra mbk-closed graphs and investigate various properties concerning of such these class of generalized graphs.

It is well known that the subset $\{(x, f(x)) \mid x \in X\} \subseteq X \times Y$ for a mapping $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is called the graph of f and is denoted via G_f .

Definition 2.1. The graph G_f of a mapping $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is said to be

(1) mbk-closed[2] if for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$, there exist mbk-open set $A \subseteq X$ and open set $B \subseteq Y$ such that $x \in A$, $y \in B$ and $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.

(2) contra δ -b-closed if for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$, there exist mbk-open set $A \subseteq Y$ and closed set $B \subseteq Z$ such that $x \in A$, $y \in B$ and $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.

Now, we give a proof which is a characterization of mbk-closed graph functions. It is given as lemma without proof in [2].

Proposition 2.2. Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ be a function. Then the graph G_f of f is mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$ iff for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$ there exist $A \in \text{MBKO}(X, x)$ and $B \in \varphi$ ($y \in B$) such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$.

Proof. We must prove that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ iff $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$. Assume that $(A \times B) \cap G_f \neq \emptyset$. Then there exist $(x, y) \in (X \times Y)$ such that $(x, y) \in (A \times B)$, $y \neq f(x)$ and $(x, y) \in G_f$. Hence $f(x) \in f(A)$. Since $f(x) \in f(A)$ and $y \in B$, $f(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$.

Proposition 2.3. The graph G_f of a mapping $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is contra mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$ iff for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$ there exist $A \in \text{MBKO}(X, x)$ and $B \in \varphi^i$ ($y \in B$) such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ (φ^i denotes the family all closed sets in (Z, ω)).

Proof. This proof is similar to that of Proposition 2.2.

Theorem 2.4. If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is mbk-continuous and (Y, φ) is T_1 -space, then G_f is contra mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$.

Proof. Let $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$. Hence $y \neq f(x)$ and since (Y, φ) is T_1 -space, there exist $B \in \varphi$ such that $f(x) \in B$ and $y \notin B$. Besides, since f is mbk-continuous, of course there exist $A \in \text{MBKO}(X, x)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq B$. Therefore, we have $f(A) \cap (Z - B) = \emptyset$ and $B \in \varphi^i$ ($y \in B$). Finally, one obtains that G_f is contra mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$ via Proposition 2.3.

Theorem 2.5. Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is a surjective which has mbk-closed graph function. Then, (Y, φ) is T_1 -space.

Proof. Assume that $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ when $y_1 \neq y_2$. Since f is a surjective function, there exists an $x_1 \in X$ so that $f(x_1) = y_1$ and $f(x_1) \neq y_2$. Hence $(x_1, y_2) \notin G_f$ and so via Proposition 2.2, there exist $A_1 \in \text{MBKO}(X, x_1)$ and $B_1 \in \varphi$ ($y_2 \in B_1$) so that $f(A_1) \cap B_1 = \emptyset$. Then $y_1 \in f(A_1)$, but $y_1 \notin B_1$. In similar way, there exists a $x_2 \in X$ so that $f(x_2) = y_2$ and $f(x_2) \neq y_1$. Then, $(x_2, y_1) \notin G_f$ and using Proposition 2.2, there exist $A_2 \in \text{MBKO}(X, x_2)$ and $B_2 \in \varphi$ ($y_1 \in B_2$) so that $f(A_2) \cap B_2 = \emptyset$. Hence $y_2 \in f(A_2)$ but $y_2 \notin B_2$. Therefore, $B_1 \in \varphi$ ($y_2 \in B_1$) and $B_2 \in \varphi$ ($y_1 \in B_2$)

but $y_1 \notin B_1$ and $y_2 \notin B_2$. This shows that (Y, φ) is T_1 -space.

Definition 2.6. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is called mbk-open if $f(U)$ is mbk-open in Y for every open sets U of X .

Theorem 2.7. If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is mbk-open and surjective function and G_f is mbk-closed graph, then (Y, φ) is mbk- T_2 -space.

Proof. Let $z_1, z_2 \in Y$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$. Since f is a surjective function, there exists an $y_1 \in Y$ so that $f(y_1) = z_1$ and $f(y_1) \neq z_2$. Hence $(y_1, z_2) \notin G_f$ and then there exist $A \in \delta BO(Y, y_1)$ and $B \in \omega(z \in B)$ so that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ by utilizing Proposition 3.2. Since f is δ -b-open function, $f(A)$ is δ -b-open set containing z_1 . According to Diagram, B is a δ -b-open set containing z_2 . Hence, (Z, ω) is δ -b- T_2 -space.

Definition 2.8. The graph G_f of a function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ will be termed strongly contra mbk-closed if for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$, there exist $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ and $B \in \varphi(y \in B)$ such that $(A \times \text{cl}(B)) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.

Regarding the strongly contra δ -b-closed graph, we can the following lemma.

Lemma 2.9. The graph G_f of a function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is strongly contra mbk-closed in $X \times Y$ if for each $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$, there exist $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ and $B \subseteq Y$ is regular closed ($y \in B$) such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$.

Definition 2.10. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ will be termed weakly mbk-continuous if each $x \in X$ and for each open set B of Y containing $f(x)$, there exist $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq \text{cl}(B)$.

Theorem 2.11. Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is weakly mbk-continuous function and (Y, φ) is Urysohn space, then G_f is strongly contra mbk-closed.

Proof. Let $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$. According to definition of G_f , $y \neq f(x)$. Since (Z, ω) is Urysohn, there exist open sets $U, V \subseteq Z$ such that $f(x) \in U$, $y \in V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Since f is weakly mbk-continuous, there exists $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ so that $f(A) \subseteq \text{cl}(U)$ and $f(A) \cap \text{cl}(V) = f(A) \cap \text{cl}(\text{int}(V)) = \emptyset$ is a regular closed set in Y . Consequently, using Lemma 2.9, obtained that G_f is strongly contra mbk-closed.

Definition 2.12. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ will be termed almost mbk-continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is mbk-open set in X for every regular open set B of Y .

Lemma 2.13. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is almost mbk-continuous iff each $x \in X$ and for each regular open set B of Y containing $f(y)$, there exist $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq B$.

Theorem 2.14. If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is almost mbk-continuous and (Y, φ) is T_2 -space, then G_f is strongly contra mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$.

Proof. Consider $(x, y) \in [(X \times Y) - G_f]$. Thus $y \neq f(x)$. Since (Y, φ) is T_2 -space; there exist open sets $U, V \subseteq Y$ such that $f(x) \in U$, $y \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. This is equivalent to $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) = \emptyset$. Besides, since f is almost mbk-continuous and V is regular open, then there exists $W \in MBKO(X, x)$ so that $f(W) \subseteq V \subseteq \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ via Lemma 2.13 This implies that $f(W) \cap \text{cl}(U) = \emptyset$ and consequently by using Lemma 2.9, we obtain G_f is strongly contra mbk-closed in $(X \times Y)$.

To obtain next two theorems, now we give a definition which is related to MBK-closed set and characterizations of this notion.

Definition 2.15. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ will be termed contra mbk-continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is mbk-closed set in X for every open set B of Y .

The next theorem can be obtained by using the same technique of the similar result involving MBK-continuity.

Theorem 2.16. For a function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ the following properties are equivalent:

- (1) f is contra mbk-continuous;
- (2) For every closed subset B of Y , $f^{-1}(B)$ is δ -open set in X ;
- (3) For each $x \in X$ and each closed subset B of Y containing $f(x)$, there exists $A \in MBKO(X, x)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq B$.

Theorem 2.17. If G_f is contra mbk-continuous, then $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \varphi)$ is contra mbk-continuous.

Proof. Consider U is an open set of Y , then $X \times U$ is an open set of $X \times Y$. According to hypothesis G_f is contra mbk-continuous, we have $f^{-1}(U) = g^{-1}(X \times U)$ is mbk-closed in X . Therefore, f is contra mbk-continuous.

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